

SCREENING, ISOLATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF POLYETHYLENE TEREPHTHALATE (PET) DEGRADING BACTERIA FROM WASTE DUMPING SITES

Raheela Mujtaba^{*1}, Muhammad Thouseef², Aisha Iqbal³, Mirza Abdul Qudoos Baig⁴,
Amna Iqbal⁵, Nimra Tahir⁶, Meerub Sarfraz⁷, Umar Rashid⁸, Minahil Fatima⁹

^{*1}Department of Environmental Science, The Islamia University Bahawalpur, Pakistan

²School of Marine Science and Engineering, Nanjing Normal University, China

^{3,5,8}Department of Zoology, Division of Science and Technology, University of Education Lahore 54600, Punjab,
Pakistan

⁴Faculty of Chemistry and Geoscience, Vilnius University, Lithuania

^{6,7}Department of Zoology, Government College Women University Sialkot, Pakistan

⁹Department of Pathology, Cholistan University of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Bahawalpur, Pakistan

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Corresponding Author: *

Raheela Mujtaba

Abstract

The ever-increasing accumulation of plastic waste has emerged as a critical global environmental concern, posing severe threats to humans, animals, and ecosystems due to the recalcitrant nature and slow degradation rate of plastics. Among various remediation strategies, microbial biodegradation offers a sustainable and eco-friendly solution. Biodegradation involves the breakdown of complex polymers into simpler compounds that can be assimilated by microbial cells for energy and growth. In the present study, the biodegradation potential of soil-isolated microorganisms, including *Bacillus* sp., *Streptococcus* sp., *Escherichia coli*, and *Staphylococcus* sp., was investigated against polyethylene terephthalate (PET) as the sole carbon source. Microbial isolates were obtained through serial dilution techniques and inoculated in liquid culture flasks containing PET films. The efficiency of bacterial strains in degrading PET was evaluated by monitoring changes in total dissolved solids (TDS), which ranged from 179.3 mg/L to 285.6 mg/L during incubation, and by determining the percentage of plastic weight loss. Morphological and biochemical characterizations, including Gram staining and assays for lipase, mannitol, citrate, catalase, and oxidase activities, were used to identify and confirm bacterial strains. Among the tested isolates, *Pseudomonas* sp. exhibited the highest degradation efficiency, achieving a 4.2% weight loss after 60 days, whereas *Staphylococcus* sp. showed the lowest at 2.5%. These findings highlight the potential of specific bacterial strains, particularly *Pseudomonas* sp., for use in the biodegradation of PET and the development of microbial strategies to mitigate plastic pollution.

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the past century, the large-scale manufacture of synthetic polymers, especially polyethylene terephthalate (PET), has greatly contributed to the global burden of plastic pollution. PET's ubiquity in the packaging industry and its use in fibers have made it one of the most persistent environmental contaminants (Nisticò, 2020). Traditional waste management methods have struggled to cope, as PET does not degrade readily and often accumulates in landfills, water bodies, and natural habitats, leading to environmental, ecological, and health challenges (Sinha et al., 2010).

Conventional disposal and recycling technologies often fail to achieve efficient PET recovery, leading to ongoing environmental degradation. Compounding this, PET's biodegradation proceeds at an extremely slow rate under natural conditions, prompting research into microbial degradation pathways (Taniguchi et al., 2019). Isolating bacterial strains capable of degrading PET from environments rich in plastic waste is challenging due to the complex microbial ecology present at "end-of-life" sites (i.e., dumps, landfills, marine littorals) where diverse microbial communities interact.

Plastic pollution does not confine itself to aquatic or terrestrial habitats alone; microplastics—particles smaller than 5 mm—are now found in both, often originating from the breakdown of larger plastic items (Ma et al., 2020). These particles are ingested by wildlife or lead to entanglement, damaging habitats and altering species interactions. Furthermore, plastics function as vectors for chemical additives (such as flame retardants, plasticizers, bisphenols, etc.) and environmental pollutants, which can bioaccumulate through food chains (Ma et al., 2020). The durability of plastics, including PET, contributes to long-term pollution, as their resistance to thermal, chemical, and photodegradation means they persist in ecosystems for decades. Alabi et al. (2019) and Beaumont et al. (2019) have reported that this persistence results in cumulative damage, economic costs (cleanup, loss to fisheries, tourism), environmental degradation, and health risks. The manufacture, use, and disposal of plastics are also significant contributors to greenhouse gas emissions, both directly (e.g., incineration) and indirectly

(through the fossil fuel-based production chain) (Shen et al., 2020).

Beyond ecological damage, there is growing evidence of direct impacts on human health. Microplastics, along with leached chemical additives like phthalates and bisphenol A (BPA), have been found in food, water, and even air, with suggested outcomes including endocrine disruption, developmental defects, inflammation, and cancer in some epidemiological and animal studies (da Costa et al., 2023). Inhalation of microplastic aerosols may pose additional risks to the respiratory and cardiovascular systems (Andrady, 2022).

From a materials perspective, plastics are categorized by their thermal behavior (thermoplastics vs. thermosets), degradability, crystallinity, molecular weight, and hydrophobicity—all factors that influence their resistance to degradation (Zhou et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2021). PET, being a semi-crystalline thermoplastic polyester, tends to resist abiotic degradation and presents a limited surface area for microbial attack unless the polymer structure is modified or pretreated.

Microorganisms, however, offer a promising route for PET degradation. The discovery of *Ideonella sakaiensis* in 2016 illustrated that bacteria can not only attach to but also enzymatically hydrolyze PET into its monomers, terephthalic acid and ethylene glycol (Yoshida et al., 2016). Other bacterial and fungal species have similarly been shown to produce enzymes (PETase and cutinases) capable of degrading PET polymers, albeit often at slow rates or under non-ideal laboratory conditions (Carr et al., 2020; Singh et al., 2020).

In this study, we focus on the screening, isolation, and biochemical characterization of PET-degrading bacteria from waste disposal sites. By surveying native microbial communities, assessing their degradative efficiency against PET, and characterizing their enzymatic and physiological profiles, this work aims to enhance understanding of PET biodegradation mechanisms. The ultimate goal is to identify strains that might be harnessed for sustainable, cost-effective bioremediation or recycling strategies.

2. Methodology

2.1. Description of the Study Area

Many distinct soil samples (10 grams each) were taken from various waste disposal facilities in The Islamia University, Bahawalpur, the dumping site of Sadar Pulli Bahawalpur, the Dumping site of Ring Road Bahawalpur, the Dumping site of Middle City Bahawalpur and Riaz Colony Hostel for this investigation. These locations were chosen because they are frequent recipients of significant amounts of plastic products. To guarantee that representative samples were taken in duplicate from multiple levels within the dumping sites. Using a sterile spatula, a sample of soil was taken from the area surrounding the plastic waste, and it was then placed in a sterile container. For this study, only drink-related plastic bottles were chosen. A PET sample was bought from a nearby market and brought into the lab.

2.2. Soil sample analysis

Physio-chemical analyses were performed on soil samples to assess a variety of parameters, including conductivity, pH, organic matter content, moisture content, and total dissolved solids.

2.2.1. Organic matter content

The amount of organic matter in the soil was measured using the following approach. Initially, each vessel was dried in the oven for an entire day at 105°C. Allow them to cool in desiccator containers after that. After cooling, each container was weighed separately. One gram of dirt was then added to each container. The soil within these containers was heated in a furnace to 115°C for thirty minutes, with periodic stirring of the soil. Allow them to cool in the desiccators and weigh them again (Oyeyiola and Agbaje, 2013).

2.4. Materials

The materials, equipment and various reagents used in different stages of this research are listed here

• Peptone	• Agar
• Beef extract	• Gram iodine
• Ethanol	• Sodium chloride
• Crystal violet	• Safranin
• Soil sample	• Diluents (sterile distilled water)

2.2.2. pH, TDS and Conductivity

To check the pH of the soil samples, 15g of each soil sample was diluted in 100ml of distilled water. The pH meter was used to record the pH of each sample. 150ml of distilled water with 50g of the soil sample was stirred for 10 minutes. The solution was filtered after 30 minutes to let the soil sit at the bottom of the beaker. The conductivity and the total dissolved solids TDS were checked and recorded with the help of a TDS meter (Corwin and Yemoto, 2020).

2.2.3. Moisture amount

To determine the soil's moisture content, the crucibles were dried in an oven heated at 105°C until they reached a steady weight, which implied full drying. The weights of each of these dehydrated crucibles were then measured individually. After that, each soil sample weighed precisely one gram and was added to the appropriate crucible. These crucibles filled with dirt were dried again in an oven that was maintained at 105°C for 24 hours. The crucibles were dried and then allowed to cool in desiccators before their weights were carefully recorded again (Oyeyiola and Agbaje, 2013).

2.3. Microbiological Analysis

The serial dilution technique was considered a promising approach to isolate and count PET-degrading bacteria from landfill sites, which were employed for this task. The subsequent gradual dilution of environmental samples resulted in the separation of the native microbial strains with PET-degrading potential, thus affirming the contention that naturally occurring microbes are capable of degrading PET. Using our identifying method, we were able to identify and characterize the bacterial strains as they appeared in terms of their morphology, colony appearance, and their biochemical properties, as briefly stated in the Bergey's manual of Systematic Bacteriology (Garrity, 2007).

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pipettes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incubator
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vortex mixture 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sterile conical flask
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Test tubes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Petri dishes

2.5. Media Preparation

Extraction was done in a fashion whereby PET-degrading bacteria that could break down PET were grown using a selective enrichment method on salt agar with minimal salt as the carbon source (MSA) that contained factors for better microbial growth. The medium was autoclaved at 121°C for 15 minutes. Following autoclaving, the agar plate was cooled to room temperature (Qiao et al., 2022). I was careful to accurately measure and prepare each nutritional component of the agar medium. About 5 grams of peptone, 3 grams of beef extract, the same amount of sodium chloride (NaCl) and boiled warm agar up to 15 grams were used in accordance with the homework procedure. The matter was considered while the sensitive weight balance was used to measure these mixtures with the precision of the closest unit of a gram. The precise measure of the parts that followed in a flask used for media preparation. It was contained in a conical flask of 1000 milliliters of purified water. Making sure that peptone, beef extract, NaCl, and agar are well mixed with the water, the predetermined quantity of each of them was added to the flask gradually, one at a time. Aluminum foil was laid over the flask opening for the whole process to avoid contamination. The agar was aseptically prepared from medium that was thoroughly mixed up and the flasks were kept sealed to ensure that the contents were sterile. A hot plate was employed to achieve an even volume of the components. By introducing in the flask, the sustaining mix of agar and cautiously covering it with aluminum foil, it was then safely placed on the hotplate. The temperature of 250°F was set, which symbolizes the sterilization temperature in most microbiological laboratories. We took off the hot plate and introduced the flask again right after 15 minutes and its content was allowed to cool to the proper temperature before being used again. Through analytical contributions of mixing, sterilizing and closing the nutrient-rich agar medium, potential contamination was decreased and the right environment for microbial development was provided.

2.6. Agar plate preparation

The most important aspect in the practical part of the microbiology study is the agar plate preparation, which of large enough to accommodate the development of all the bacteria (Kumar et al., 2012). Nutrient agar, commonly, is regarded as the growth medium that contains necessary nutrients for bacterial growth, and this was used in the current study. The precise amount of ingredients (, peptone, beef extract, and NaCl) was used for nutrient agar preparation using distilled water. The solution was then transferred to clean plates after the sterility process and mixing was done for a long time. To ensure a high-quality growth medium, the addition of agar was done very carefully to maximize the overall agar distribution in the petri dish. Agar was added to the Petri plates and when hardened got a gel-like characteristic and changed its consistency from liquid to solid. The agar plates were then incubated for about five to ten minutes because colony formation is dependent on the environment and the plate's temperature. Stabilizing bacteria against dispersion through the surface is the main reason for the solidification of agar. To avoid the agar disintegrating because of the liquefaction due to incubation, the agar must be properly solidified.

2.7. Use of Laminar Airflow Cabinet

To maintain sterility and prevent the introduction of contaminants, the entire process of adding agar to Petri plates and transferring them to the incubator was carried out following strict aseptic procedures. With a biosafety cabinet, a sterile condition was established in a regulated work area. By filtering the airflow from the work area through the laminar circulation channels, the possibility of the agar plates' direct cross-contamination with airborne pollutants was minimized (Mcdade et al., 1968).

2.8. Storage in Incubator at 37°C

Once the agar had set, the Petri plates were taken to the incubator and heated to 37°C. It is likely that for several replicate bacterial species that are typically investigated, their growth was best at 37 °C. The incubator paved the way to sterilizing the bacteria

from any chance of contamination, and at the same time bolstered their growth rate through the provision of an unchanging environment with regulated facilitation.

2.9. Serial Dilution Technique

The procedure of the serial dilution was used to determine the viable bacterial count, the quantity of them in each sample. This counting method forms a fundamental cellular-level microbiological method and involves the dilution of the sample to the extent that is possible on an agar plate (Lin et al., 2021). It plays the most important role when there are too many microorganisms in a sample. It helps to distinguish colonies and to find out the microbial count. Microbial count in samples provides us with essential information. The trial matrix for bacterial enumeration is the key one in dilution serial sequencing. After that it is chosen to use a conical flask, sterile and the volume of water is 50 ml of distilled sterile water. Next, the soil is completely digested to make sure that the classified colony is correctly proclaimed. The secondary step aimed to assist the solute to break up into a uniform distribution and even more mixing was employed.

When performing the serial dilution technique, there must be safely maintain bacterial cell viability while continually monitoring the bacterial cell amounts. 0.47 fluid ounces of sterile distilled water is poured in a test tube, then each reagent is added. With the use of a sterile pipette or transfer pipette, one ml of the sample was diluted by transferring directly to the second one after mixing it properly. By means of mixing the diluted mixture a second time after this step ensures proper distribution of the sample of water in the second tube. By the end of the exercise, only the test tubes previously diluted had been moved from each of the dilutions to the sequential dilution, thus going from one test tube to another. Specific proportion and accurate emptying should be achieved during the transfer procedure, which allows achieving standardization and homogeneity. Then, the process of the serial dilutions was carried out; the diluted samples were set as well, and took place on the agar plates (Roslan, 2013).

2.10. Inoculation, incubation and sub-culturing

The Streak Plate Method was employed to make singular junkyards of mixed cultures out of a single colony (Jasson et al., 2010). Only a minute part of the microbial culture was recognized and isolated with a sterile inoculating loop. Then it was streaked across the growth medium of the agar plate culture. To ensure the proper distribution of bacteria over the whole surface of the Petri dish, the streaking has been made in a zig-zag direction. This stir was intended to do the following: to dilute the bacterial culture and stimulate the development of the single colonies. It is essential to set the temperature for the incubation and inoculate the petri dishes with it. Cells of a certain bacterial strain were designated to multiply and form specific colonies, growing on the agar's surface during this period.

Finally, the bacteria incubated were inspected while their plates were also streaked into the same media to grow pure cultures. Using a well-sterilized inoculation loop, we were blending well-isolated colonies that were visible on our streaked plates and moved those colonies into new petri dishes that had agar medium in their innermost part to avoid the contamination of bacterial colonies and to investigate and test our sole bacterial colonies.

2.11. Biochemical tests:

To identify and categorize bacterial strains, the Gram staining procedure and biochemical tests were very critical steps in my exploration. Through the investigation of microbial species behaviors such as their habitat, traits, and other characteristics, microbiological sciences gained an edge ahead of others and this knowledge is now applied to various biology-related fields.

2.11.1. Gram Staining Procedure:

Gram Staining, established as the classic differentiation technique of microorganisms, is performed by determining bacteria as either being Gram-positive or Gram-negative, depending on their cell wall structures. The procedure was done by wiping glass slides wipe off using ethyl alcohol 75%, smeared with bacterial culture with drop-wise distilled water, then dried under heat with crystal violet dye, and treated with Gram's iodine solution. After that, colored smears were washed again with 95% ethanol

to make them color-free. The cognate dye retains the hue in the case of Gram-positive bacteria, whereas the safranin dye deposits in the opposite scenario with Gram-negative bacteria. After that, the slides were scanned to classify and identify bacterial cells by their form and the act of stains.

2.11.2. Catalase Test

The catalase test is a crucial biochemical test in microbiology that differentiates bacteria based on their ability to produce the catalase enzyme (Reineke, 2001). It involves introducing hydrogen peroxide to bacterial smears, then observing the reaction.

Hydrogen peroxide was broken down into oxygen and water by this enzyme. To produce even layers of bacterial growth, the colonies were moved onto clean glass slides using a sterile inoculating loop. The following stage involved covering each species' bacterial smear with two to three drops of 3% hydrogen peroxide without mixing. *Staphylococcus* smears showed bubbles of oxygen gas, indicating positive catalase reactions. *Streptococcus* smears showed no bubbles, indicating a deficiency. The test is simple, quick, and allows quick separation of bacterial isolates.

Figure 2.1: Catalase test

2.11.3. Mannitol Salt Agar Test

Mannitol Salt Agar was created by combining and weighing various ingredients, including peptone, agar, sodium chloride, D-mannitol, phenol red, and beef extract (Kateete et al., 2010). These ingredients were thoroughly combined to ensure homogeneity. The mixture was then autoclaved for 15 minutes at 121°C to sanitize and remove any contaminating microbes. After autoclaving, the medium was allowed to cool to a temperature of 45 to 50°C to prevent early solidification. To make agar plates, the sterilized media was transferred to sterile petri dishes. The medium was distributed evenly across each plate to guarantee uniform thickness. After being left to fully firm at room temperature, the agar plates were then chilled at 2–8°C until required.

Except for the halophilic species like *Staphylococci*, the selective action of sodium chloride in MSA

inhibited the growth of most bacteria, making it easier to isolate. Moreover, the unique properties of D-mannitol made it easier to separate bacteria based on how well they could ferment mannitol. Pathogenic *Staphylococcus aureus* can ferment mannitol, resulting in acidic byproducts that lower the pH of the medium and cause phenol red, a pH indicator, to turn yellow.

2.11.4. Lipase Test

A Lipase Test was carried out to isolate and characterize PET-degrading bacteria to evaluate the enzymatic activity of the isolated bacterial strains (Vague et al., 2019). Enzymes called lipases catalyze the hydrolysis of lipid ester linkages, which break down fats and oils into smaller molecules. Within the framework of this investigation, the Lipase Test assisted in ascertaining the isolated bacteria's capacity to generate lipase enzymes, which are crucial for the breakdown of PET. The bacterial isolates are cultivated in media containing lipid substrates, such as olive oil or tributyrin, for the Lipase Test. Following

an incubation period, hydrolysis clear zones that appear around bacterial colonies indicate the existence of lipase activity (Anbalagan et al., 2021). However, lipid molecules are broken down by the lipase enzymes produced by bacteria, which leads to fatty acid release, and further hydrolysis of these fatty acids leads to the formation of these zones.

2.11.5. Oxidase Test

The identification of the catalase enzyme was conducted by the Oxidase test on filter paper, with Kovacs' reagents prepared freshly (Sharma et al., 2014). The immersion of the perforated filter paper in the reagent of choice was followed by the transfer of a tiny part of the bacterial culture to the reagent-treated paper.

2.11.6. Citrate Test

The Citrate Utilization Test is the test used for ascertaining if a particular organism can develop sources of primary energy from citrates or not. In this test, Citrate agar becomes the medium. Further, this medium consisted of a carbon source, primarily as citrate and ammonium salts, as the main nitrogen (Wanger et al., 2017). For performing the test, the sample in the middle of the colony was taken using the loop and inoculated with its tip on the slant agar surface, followed by incubating at 37°C for a duration ranging from 4 to 7 days. As visualized, evidence was

provided by the appearance of a green-to-blue change in the color of the agar.

2.12. Pre-treatment of Plastic Samples:

The PET bottles got some cutting treatment up to the length of the strips, which thereafter went into a beaker full of distilled water, where they were stirred for an hour. Next, the cotton balls were put into the ethanol solution, with a concentration of 75% of ethanol v/v, for 30 minutes, with the target to disinfect and completely remove any residual organic substances adhering to the PET surface. Once this is done, the next step was that the PET strips were placed on a sterile absorbent pad. Finally, the plastic strips were left to air-dry and weighed to achieve a consistent mass.

2.13. Determination of weight loss

A conical flask filled with 50 mL of culture broth medium was aseptically filled with pre-weighed strains made from polythene bags that had been infected with various bacterial species. In the control group, plastic discs were kept in a microbial-free medium. For every treatment, separate flasks were kept and placed in a shaker. The plastic strains were collected after a month of shaking, properly cleaned with distilled water, dried in the shade, and then weighed to determine their final weight (Divyalakshmi and Subhashini, 2016). The weight loss of the plastics was computed using the data gathered (Thakur, 2012).

3. Results

3.1. Analysis of Soil Sample Physicochemical Characteristics

Table 3.1: Analysis of Soil Sample Physicochemical Characteristics

Characteristics	Soil sample No.				
	1	2	3	4	5
Type of Soil	Clay	Sandy	Loamy	Sandy	Loamy
Color	Reddish Brown	Light Brown	Dark Brown	Brown	Brown
Texture	Fine	Fine	Coarse	Coarse	Fine
pH	7.5	7.3	7.2	7.4	7.3

TDS mg/l	271.2±58.2	179.3±120.4	245.6±86.5	269.7±140.5	285.6±98.2
Temperature	26.20±0.14	26.05±1.00	26.13±0.37	26.05±1.00	26.18±0.16
Electrical conductivity (µS/cm)	350.2±130.2	473.4±200.2	398.4±134.8	523.4±184.2	469.1±236.0
Locations	Dumping site of Riaz Colony Hostel	Dumping site of Islamia University, Bahawalpur	Dumping site of Sadar Pulli, Bahawalpur	Dumping site of Ring Road Bahawalpur	Dumping site of middle city Bahawalpur

Physicochemical characterization attributed in Table 3.1, gives soil samples from various samples on diverse attributes. Every soil sample was marked by a unique number and had specific properties concerning the color, structure, and environmental conditions. One sample exemplifies clay soil with a fine texture and reddish-brown color. Sand grain was represented by the appearance of another sample in a fine texture, but with a light brown color. In the second place, Sample 3, which was the representative of loamy soil, has a dark brown color and a coarse texture, while Sample 4 and 5, were the sandy and loamy soils, respectively along with their brown hues and different textures the exact replicas of Sample 4 and 5. Taking into consideration the pH levels of all samples, which

range between 7.2 to 7.5, the soil's alkalinity can be regarded as slightly alkaline across the land sites examined. The water TDS values displayed a variability during the sampling, showing the concentrations varying from 179.3 mg/l to 285.6 mg/l. Likewise, the electrical conductivity, which normally remains almost undiscerning and approximately 26°C, is less constant among soil samples, thus indicating that it also varies depending on the soil's conductivity property. Scientific results have pinpointed the differentiability characteristics of the soil at the selected plots, indicating, among others, the effects of the soil matter composition and of the local weather and climate conditions on the ecosystem.

Table 3.2: Organic Matter and Moisture Content Percentage across Dumpsites

Soil Sample	Organic Matter (%)	Moisture Content (%)
1	0.42	0.43
2	0.80	0.25
3	0.24	0.87
4	0.88	1.81
5	0.30	0.04

For Sample 1, the organic matter content was shown to be 0.42% and the moisture content to be 0.43%, which was a bit higher than what was generally observed on average. Unlike in Soil Sample 2 where organic matter content increased up to 0.8% and its moisture level was at 0.25%, Soil Sample 3 showed

the opposite end with less organic matter content at 0.24% and it was also the same as the moisture level at 0.87%. Soil Sample 4 represented a higher level of organic matter in a percentage of 0.88% and a higher level of moisture on a unit of 1.81%. The organic matter content for Sampling 5 was highly elevated,

0.88%. Other samples had less organic matter content because that was 0.88%, the highest moisture content among all samples was recorded for the same sample, which is 1.81%. Indisputably, Sample 5 was the one with organic matter having moderate content, which was equal to 0.30%, and, at the same time, the least moisture content witnessed among all samples, this

being with a figure of 0.04%. This overall shows that pressures can differ greatly from one side to of the soil samples, due to the different environmental conditions, waste composition, or the way the site was managed across these landfills.

3.2 Morphology Analysis

Table 3.3: Colony morphology of the bacterial strain based on serial dilution

Sr. No.	Dilution No.	Colony morphology	Source
1	10 ⁻¹ -10 ⁻⁴	Large irregular cream	Dumping site of Riaz Colony Hostel
		Small punctiform white	
		Large elongated yellow	
		Large spreading pale yellow	
2	10 ⁻¹ -10 ⁻⁴	Small circular white	Dumping site of Islamia University, Bahawalpur
		Large, irregular, pale yellow	
		Large spreading cream	
		Large elongated yellow	
3	10 ⁻¹ -10 ⁻⁴	Large irregular cream	Dumping site of Sadar Pulli, Bahawalpur
		Small circular white	
		Large spreading pale yellow	
		Large, elongated, pale yellow	
4	10 ⁻¹ -10 ⁻⁴	Small circular cream	Dumping site of Ring Road, Bahawalpur
		Large spreading yellow	
		Small punctiform pale yellow	
		Large irregular white	
5	10 ⁻¹ -10 ⁻⁴	Small circular cream	Dumping site of Middle City Bahawalpur
		Large elongated yellow	
		Large spreading yellow	
		Long pale yellow	

The soil samples collected from the different locations in the four haulage areas were subjected to the morphology analysis of the molds obtained from them and resulted to assorted patterns as evident from Table 3.3. The dumping site of Riaz Colony Hostel was subjected to a few dilutions; these were further inspected at the laboratory and exhibited large irregular cream, small punctiform white, large elongated yellow, and large spreading pale yellow colony morphologies. Diversity of recovered organisms might reflect the presence of a multitude of microorganisms in this environment, potentially resulting in microbial interaction due to factors such as waste composition, moisture, and temperature fluctuations, among others. There is an observation of circular-yellow; irregular-white colonies, which show a complex microbial community. This microbial population is adapted to the unique conditions at this dumping site. These areas from the dumping site north of Islamia University, Bahawalpur, had irregular big white colonies 10⁻¹ -10⁻⁴. This uniformity in the dumpsite colonies suggests that the Islamia University of Bahawalpur, the microbial community, is the one specialized to the prevailing this location. The mass of the alipino population may be an index of a dominant microorganism species in this situation. So far am

allowed only to add up with further doses of dilution no. The dumping site of sadar pulli Bahawalpur again shows another trend from 10⁻¹ to 10⁻⁴. In these colonies, Large elongated pale-yellow formations are mainly evident in number. This unique morphological display differs in terms of types of waste or specific environmental problems and implies that the microbial community that exists there has been affected in one way or another due to differing variations in types of waste or specific environmental conditions. Furthermore, dilution No. By visiting 10⁻¹ to 10⁻⁴ dumps at Ring Road Bahawalpur, we observed a combination of a large white clumpy mass and a small punctiform pale yellow mass. This implies that a wide range of distinct microorganisms are present there, probably because of the fact that they are more accustomed to the environment of the dumpsite, which contains different types of organic matter. Finally, samples taken from the Bahawalpur city middle area dumping site also came up with mainly large yellow colonies at different dilutions, spreading on some elongated yellow and Small circular white ones. Similar microbial species diversity, which can be a result of the dissimilar composition of different waste constituents present at the site or distinct environmental parameters, is another indication of microbes differentiating their habitats.

Figure 3.1: Subculturing of microbes differentiating their habitats.

Figure 3.2: Colony morphology of the strains based on serial dilution.

3.3. Biochemical tests and Gram Staining

Table 3.4: Results of Biochemical tests and Gram staining

Biochemical Tests	Strain No.					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Catalase Test	+	+	+	+	+	+
Mannitol Test	+	-	+	-	+	+
Lipase Test	+	+	+	+	+	+
Citrate Test	+	+	-	+	-	+
Oxidase Test	+	-	+	+	-	+
Gram stain	-	-	+	-	+	-
Color	Pink	Pink	Purple	Pink	Purple	Pink
Shape	Cocci	Cocci	Rods	Rods	Rods	Cocci
Probable Organism	<i>Streptococcus</i>	<i>Staphylococcus sp.</i>	<i>Proteus</i>	<i>Pseudomonas</i>	<i>Bacillus sp.</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>

Among all the samples taken, *Bacillus*, *Staphylococcus*, *Streptococcus*, *Proteus*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Escherichia coli* were found in all the study locations. The results of microorganisms have been summarized in Table 3.4 in which the outcomes of biochemical and Gram tests of six different microbial strains are illustrated. The catalase test on all the organisms showed the existence of catalase activity with ammonia gas being the byproduct after hydrogen peroxide reacted with them. Also, we conducted the Mannitol Test, which gave a positive result in all the strains, indicating that all of them can consume Mannitol. The Lipase Test was positive for all strains, too, which means that their potential to break down lipids is also there. Strain 6 tested for the capability of citrate utilization, which was positive; however, strains 3 and 5 were negative, which might be proof that they have dissimilar capabilities of metabolic process. Additionally, the Oxidase activity turned out to be distributed unevenly across subspecies, thus for some strains it tested

positive while others did not. Additional Gram staining provided identification of the strains as they stained Gram-positive in Strains 1, 2, 4 and 6 whereas Strains 3 and 5 were Gram-negative. Over microscopic examination, color and size differences among strains of color of them, lower than colonies, were shown in more pinkish and cocci-shaped ones by Strains 1, 2, 4 and 6, and some purple rod-shaped ones by Strains 3 and 5. Also, based on this data, it was determined that bacteria belonging to the genus *Streptococcus* were for Strain 1, genus *Staphylococcus* was for Strain 2, the group of bacteria from species *Proteus* was for Strains 3, from species *Pseudomonas* for Strains 4, from the species *Bacillus* for Strains 5 and *Escherichia coli* was found. However, the toxicants, all in all, revealed key biochemical features and could potentially be used in establishing the microorganisms as definite based on the samples.

Figure 3.3: Gram staining of the selected isolated strains

3.4. Weight Loss

The values of polyethylene terephthalate and those of polystyrene as well as the time intervals required for their degradation were investigated by various

bacterial strains and the results are tabulated in Tables 3.5, 3.6, 3.7, Figures 3.1 and 3.2, and also in Figure 3.3.

Table 3.5: Result of Polystyrene degradation by bacteria after different time

Strain no.	Initial wt (g)	Polystyrene					Difference
		Weight (g) of bottle strips after					
		15d	30d	45d	60d		
1	1	0.990	0.985	0.980	0.970	0.03	
2	1	0.993	0.989	0.985	0.975	0.025	
3	1	0.989	0.981	0.978	0.967	0.033	
4	1	0.987	0.980	0.971	0.958	0.06	
5	1	0.988	0.984	0.976	0.962	0.038	
6	1	0.980	0.975	0.970	0.960	0.04	

As Table 3.5, which highlights the effect of polystyrene degradation on PET strips, shows, there was a decrease in the weight of all stripes on each strain.

4 demonstrated the highest weight loss percentage at 4.2% after 60 days, while strain 2 showed the lowest at 2.5%.

Figure 3.4: Degradation percentage graph of polystyrene's different strains

Table 3.6: Result of PET degradation by bacteria after different time (Plastic Bottle)

Strain no.	Initial wt (g)	Plastic Bottle					Difference
		Weight (g) of Bag strips after				Difference	
		15d	30d	45d	60d		
1	1	0.992	0.987	0.982	0.972	0.028	
2	1	0.995	0.991	0.987	0.977	0.023	
3	1	0.991	0.983	0.980	0.969	0.031	
4	1	0.989	0.982	0.973	0.960	0.04	
5	1	0.990	0.986	0.978	0.964	0.036	
6	1	0.982	0.977	0.972	0.962	0.038	

Similarly, in Table 3.6, representing degradation in plastic bottles, all strains also exhibited a decrease in

the weight of the PET strips over time. Strain 4 again showed the highest weight loss percentage at 4% after 60 days, and strain 2 showed the lowest at 2.3%.

Figure 3.5: Degradation percentage graph of plastic bottle's different strains

Table 3.7: Result of PET degradation by bacteria after different times (Plastic Bag)

Strain no.	Initial wt (g)	Plastic Bags					Difference
		Weight (g) of bottle strips after					
		15d	30d	45d	60d		
1	1	0.988	0.983	0.978	0.968	0.032	
2	1	0.991	0.987	0.983	0.973	0.027	
3	1	0.987	0.979	0.976	0.965	0.035	
4	1	0.985	0.978	0.969	0.956	0.044	
5	1	0.986	0.982	0.974	0.960	0.04	
6	1	0.978	0.973	0.968	0.958	0.042	

Table 3.7 represents degradation in plastic bags; all strains also exhibited a decrease in the weight of the PET

strips over time. Strain 4 again showed the highest weight loss percentage at 4.4% after 60 days, and Strain 2 showed the lowest at 2.7%.

Figure 3.6: Degradation percentage graph of plastic bag's different strains

Figure 3.7: Comparative degradation percentage of all three plastics

The Comparison of degradation efficiency between three different types of plastic materials reflects that

the degradation of PET in plastic bags was slightly higher compared to plastic bottles and polystyrene for most strains, as shown in Figure 3.8.

Figure 3.8: Plastic bottles and polystyrene degradation

This could be due to differences in surface area, accessibility of the PET material to bacterial strains, or other environmental factors. Analyzing the contribution of the bacterial strains to PET degradation, it can be inferred that the Gram-positive *Bacillus* and *Proteus* strains (Strain 3 and Strain 5) showed notable degradation efficiency, especially in plastic bags. Gram-negative *Pseudomonas* strains (Strain

4) also exhibited significant degradation capability, particularly in plastic bags. Gram-negative Cocci and *Escherichia coli* strains (Strains 1 and 6) performed moderately well to very well in molecular degradation efficiency in all the empty water and food packaging wastes, condiment bottles, bags, polystyrene, etc. Strain 2 -term Gram-negative *Staphylococcus* sp. had

the lowest degradation efficiency among others, which was sustained in the degradation of both PLA and PE.

4. Discussion

The exhaustive exploration of screening, selecting, and determining traits of bacteria that degrade polyethylene terephthalate collected from dumping sites can provide vital information needed to address the current increasing challenges of plastic pollution. This work considers the ability of the bacterial cultured strains for PET degradation, detailing findings, a thorough comprehension of capabilities and implications through examination of the colony shape, undertaking Gram stain and a degradation investigation. It can be deduced that the soil quality is diverse in different areas within the investigated area, which may be indicated by different soil types, the ploughing, the layout of the land, and the local climate which resulting in various soil properties such as soil color and texture, pH, TDS, temperature, and electric conductivity (Gul et al., 2015). The area under study contains different types of soils, silty, sandy, and clay earth, etc., which illustrates the level of complexity of a soil matrix. A sandy soil generally has a more robust texture and a lesser capacity for holding water, while clayey soils, on the other hand, have a finer texture and are perfect in retaining water. With sand, silt, and clay comprising loam soils, they often provide optimal conditions for plant development and nutrient storage (Jiang and Mitsch 2020). The samples exhibit reddish brown to dark brown soils, which were indicative of changes in amounts of organic matter, mineral content and also oxidizing processes and available microbes within the soil profile (Vepraskas et al., 2016).

Soil samples collected from indigenous dumpsites gave the results of slightly alkaline pH with a range from 7.2 to 7.5. The range agrees well with the alkaline soils in this region. Microbe actions, nutrient absorbability and in general, the soil are simply a function of environmental conditions in the soil (Gondal et al., 2021). The microbial composition and performance within soil can be impeded by the utilization of different fertilizer types, the application of chemicals and the modification of pH levels, resulting in the inability of plants to absorb the nutrients properly when the pH level significantly changes (Ferrarezi et al., 2022). In addition, the extent

of the migration and amount of pollution directly available to humans is influenced by the type of soil, whether it is acidic or alkaline which can majorly affect the remediation plan as well as the final assessment for the environmental risk analysis (Sherene 2010).

The TDS values displayed a variability during the sampling, showing the concentrations varying from 179.3 mg/l to 285.6 mg/l. In Soil Sample 1, the results indicated slightly higher than average organic matter content of 0.42% and moisture content of 0.43%. In contrast to Soil Sample 2, which has an organic matter content of up to 0.8% and a moisture level of 0.25%, Soil Sample 3 has a lower organic matter content of 0.5% and the same moisture level of 0.25%. As measured in percentage terms, Soil Sample 3 has a lower organic matter content (0.24%) and a higher moisture content (0.87%). Sampling 4 was found to have the highest organic matter content of 0.88%. The sample with the highest moisture content (1.81%) out of all the samples was the same one. Among all the samples, Sample 5 has the lowest moisture content, measuring approximately 0.04%. It is also the sample with the most moderate organic matter content, at 0.30%.

This extensive variation in morphologies observed among the isolates reveals the well-known adaptability and fortitude of microbial communities to withstand the hardships of their environment, conditioned by waste repositories. Enlarged yellow with irregular white and very long pale-yellow colonies on the left, right and middle part of the image are clearly seen, thus the various aspects of phenotypes play a dominant role in the survival of bacterial species. Bacterial communities' diversity is indicated by their physical variations, in which the genetic factors acting on the adaptive mechanism can also be observed (Marzuki et al., 2021). Finally, the optimal methods for microbiology, Gram staining, identify the specific physical features of the isolated strains. The comparison of Gram-positive strain (3) and the Gram-negative ones shows that rather than having similar genotypes, these communities are created from organisms with different genotypes. Besides, the visible intra-group genomic differences in *Bacillus*, *Staphylococcus*, *Streptococcus*, *Proteus*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Escherichia coli* indicate the level of taxonomy in the bacterial communities acquired from different forms

of waste (Maheswaran et al., 2023). This information confirms the multifaceted character of nutritional influence on bacterial physiology and even opens the possibility of relationships between metabolic processes and coloring properties.

Soft drink bottles, hard plastic and Styrofoam packages, plastics can be found in various kinds of consumer goods as well as in the packaging, which are of concern for environmental reasons and human health (Chaukura et al., 2016). Microorganisms, including bacteria, archaea, and fungi, are a group of species that hold the clue for the decomposition of plastic into smaller components and mineralize them to transform plastic into a harmless substance (Schmaltz et al., 2020). The diversity of plastic-eating bacteria's enzymatic efficiencies calls for variations in the enzyme activity, substrate preferences, and metabolic pathways that are involved in plastic degradation (Urbanek et al., 2018). Similarly, gram-positive *Bacilli* and the *Proteus* strains are found to be quite efficient in breaking down plastic bags. Vesting these species with bioremediation potential in eliminating plastic waste becomes evident (Kale et al. 2015). Gram-negative *Pseudomonas* strains also have the equivalent degradation capability of plastic bags, mainly and this reveals much more involvement in the systems of breaking plastic (Wilkes and Aristilde 2017).

A rigorous 3-month process, during which the degree of degradation is assessed using degradation experiments, imposes a baseline for evaluating PET degradability by the isolated bacterial strains. The observed loss of weight in the plastic samples confirms the existence of microorganisms that can perform biochemical degradation of PET. Interestingly, strain 48 manifests as equally the leading one, with a projected weight loss percentage being the largest among the rest. Consequently, this shows that they excel at the degradation of the PET, a clear advantage of their metabolic proficiency. It constitutes a promising tool for future bioremediation research. The level of reduction that was noticed over a given period in time (polystyrene and PET straps shows that those bacterial strains were efficient, as they can destroy those materials that are as tough as polymers (Aversa et al., 2022). There was a relative decrease in the weight of all stripes on each identified strain. Strain 4 demonstrated the highest weight loss

percentage at 4.2% after 60 days, while Strain 2 showed the lowest at 2.5%. This overall result demonstrates how the various environmental factors, waste composition, and site management practices across these landfills can cause significant differences in the characteristics of soil samples from one side to the other.

While different types of plastic serve different functions and their degradation rates vary, there is still a disparity between the efficiency of degradation of PET in plastic bags versus its efficiency of degradation in plastic bottles and polystyrene products, as shown by the testing. Three factors explained the difference in such plastic degradation: surface area, material of the plastic, and environmental agents like moisture content, pH, and temperature (Taghavi et al., 2021). This implies that the real reason for the difference in the weight loss of various bacterial strains is also due to the complex process with multiple interactions of producing PET into an environmentally safe product (Danso et al., 2018).

Through their nature, the surrounding environmental situations, the range of the substrates they can work on, the employed enzymes and metabolic pathways, these bacterial populations shape a complicated degradation rate. Through combining techniques of colony morphology, Gram staining features, and degradation activity, a thorough description of the connectedness between the bacterial phenotype and the PET degradation capacity can be found (Ng, 2014). It seems that, in this case, the research opens the door to more specific studies, usable for various research and industrial applications. Briefly, it can be inferred that microbial biodegradation is a promising, efficient procedure for plastic waste treatment that is not only environmentally friendly but also eco-friendly. To make post-consumer plastics biodegradable, it would be practical to melt plastic materials with additives that aid the natural initiation of breakdown, to boost the biodegradation mechanisms, identify the mechanisms behind plastic breakdown, and scale up bioremediation methods to the practical level.

5. Implications and Future Directions

This study is not only of academic importance, but it is an essential step towards reducing plastic litter and, therefore, for environmental protection. A trace of

positive aspects related to plastic pollution is by fact that microbes able to degrade PET were discovered and characterized out of waste disposal locations, hoping that other riches of unrecognized bacterial diversities are waiting. Decoding the fuzzy genetic details obstructing PET decomposition will rely on advanced molecular tools, including transcriptomics, proteomics and metagenomics. Therefore, this approach would become an efficient substitute for the enzyme manufacture by means of the usage of microbial fermentation, in turn, would give grounds for biotechnology development. Additionally, the upgrading of growth conditions, substrate concentrations and consortia associations could increase the scalability and the capability of PET bioremediation technologies by offering new pathways for environmentally friendly waste management. Implementation of microbial biotechnology to solve the plastic crisis requires the convergence and development of interdisciplinary teams and technological innovations accompanied by ecological responsiveness. Concisely, the implications of the work illustrated the importance of microbial communities in building environmental resilience and promoting the sustainability of ecosystems. Our intervention is based on the powerful change of landscape to address the urgent problems of marine plastic pollution and make our world a more sustainable and cleaner place through the initial joining of scientists and later all people.

Conclusion

The study successfully isolated and characterized PET-degrading bacteria from various soil samples obtained from waste dumping sites rich in plastic materials. Morphological characterization revealed distinct colony morphologies among the bacterial strains, aiding in their identification and classification. Gram staining analysis identified the bacterial strains as either Gram-positive or Gram-negative, with variation in shape and color indicating diverse microbial populations. Biochemical tests, including catalase, mannitol, and lipase assays, demonstrated metabolic capabilities of the isolated strains, such as catalase enzyme activity and mannitol fermentation. The results showed that all tested strains exhibited positive reactions for catalase and mannitol tests, indicating their potential for plastic degradation. Degradation

experiments over 2 months revealed varying degrees of plastic weight loss, with certain strains exhibiting higher degradation efficiencies compared to others. Strains having *Bacillus* and *coccus* demonstrated the highest plastic degradation rates, suggesting their potential application in plastic waste management. The result helps to influence the perception that the individual bacterial species screened for have a potential for biodegradation of all PET plastics, which signifies an effective way of dealing with plastic pollution. Furthermore, future studies can be designed to identify the true modes of action of microbial strains in the destruction of plastic molecules and for them to be implemented in the large-scale clean-up approach. This study paved the way for new researchers to synthesize inexpensive bacteria from soil for the eco-friendly degradation of plastic.

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